

AN HF PACKET NETWORK FOR THE SOUTHERN EUROPEAN TASK FORCE

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ABSTRACT. The U.S. Army, Southern European Task Force (SETAF) has command elements located in remote areas in Italy, Greece and Turkey. These sites are plagued with poor communication, which frequently results in communication outages. This substandard situation has impacted on both the tactical and administrative performance of these units.

HF Packet Radio equipment was purchased for SETAF Headquarters in Vicenza, Italy. The objective of the program is to demonstrate the capability of HF packet radio to function as a base command, control and administrative communication system. The HF packet radio system provides a voice and a data capability, using commercial grade, state-of-the-art HF communication transceivers with packet controllers.

I. INTRODUCTION

The HF radio band is expected to play an important role in improving communications for an increasing number of military and civilian users. The characteristics of the HF band are such that it will require detailed considerations of propagation anomalies, as well as an ability to transmit messages on highly congested channels. Packet radio provides very efficient spectrum usage. There can be several stations on the same frequency and their packets will interleave. The packets are bursty in nature, and a controller listens on a frequency for a clear channel before transmitting. The most significant advantage of packet radio is its ability to store and forward messages between members of a net. Messages may be routed within the net to the destination member, or if transmission is impossible at any given time, messages can be stored on a bulletin board for off-line retrieval. The packet system can be fully automated and provide communication on a nearly uninterrupted basis.

Packet Radio is a form of communication in which messages are formed on a computer or data terminal. The messages are then fed into a data controller that includes a built-in modem for packet radio operation. The data controller converts serial, asynchronous, ASCII data to AX.25 packet radio protocol. In addition to the information provided by the computer, each packet contains addressing, error-checking and control information. The error-checking information allows the receiving station to evaluate the accuracy of the transmitted packet and determine if the received packet contained any errors. The

receiving station requests a retransmission until the packet is received error-free.

HF PACKET RADIO DEMONSTRATION

Fig. 1

SETAF has selected five sites that function as the test-bed for the demonstration system. The distance between

HF PACKET RADIO DEMONSTRATION SYSTEM

Fig. 2

sites varies between 50 and 1100 km. The system is expected to expand in the future and there will be a gateway site established in each country. The Gateway's contain an electronic bulletin board and the conventional packet radios either communication in real-time or post messages for each other for off-line usage. Because of the distances that exist between Gateway sites, a linear amplifier has been built into the Gateway hardware. Remote sites communicate in real-time with other remote sites. In the event the desired remote site cannot be contacted, the transmitting remote site will place the message on the network bulletin board at the Gateway. Remote sites are

12.2.1

directed to interrogate their bulletin boards periodically to look for messages. The Packet sites are presently operating with a broad-banded folded dipole antenna. A tunable compact loop antenna is being tried at all the sites.

The SHAPE Technical Center at the Hague has initiated an effort titled, "*The STC Packet Radio Initiative*," and has received interest from a number of US Government Agencies. Although this effort is not related to the SETAF program, the lessons learned will contribute to an improved packet network for SETAF. The US Army, Navy, Air Force, Canadian Research Center (CRC-Ottawa), and various representatives from private industry in a number of NATO countries have installed packet stations and formed a network. STC views AX.25 as an existing HF packet protocol which is used throughout the amateur and commercial radio industry. AX.25 is considered a starting point from which a more advanced, state-of-the-art packet protocol can be developed.

This paper will also address the need for propagation prediction algorithms to be integrated into each member site's computer. PC versions of IONCAP are available for inclusion into the software that resides in the packet computer. There are a number of alternative prediction systems that are under consideration.

II. ADAPTIVE SYSTEMS

There were many choices of system configurations when the decision was made to develop the network. An idea initially considered was the active utilization of more than one frequency. The transceiver under computer control could function as a scanner and monitor a number of frequencies. Because of the unpredictable nature of HF propagation, there is a need to rely upon a prediction system for an estimate of frequencies which have a calculable expectation of working. Messages could then be transmitted on more than one frequency and the packet software could decide for itself, in terms of error free traffic, an acceptable transmitting frequency. A prediction system would initially select frequencies that are likely to operate. The frequency band as selected by the prediction system could then be compared with the list of authorized frequencies. The new list that is the result of this comparison becomes the test frequencies of the adaptive radio system. This would significantly reduce the number of frequencies to be scanned. Many HF prediction systems have been implemented on the personal computer. We are presently reviewing the accuracy of the following MUF predictors: 1) the IPS System (Harrison and Turner, 1972), called SAPS, 2) IONCAP (Teters et al, 1983), 3) MINIMUF (Rose et al, 1978; Rose and Martin, 1978), and 4) MINIFTZ4 (Damboldt and Suessman, 1986).

The HF prediction system will be integrated into the menu driven packet software. Each net member will have their geographical coordinates entered into the program. With the exception of the IONCAP algorithm, the prediction systems could be performed in real-time. Possibly a

better idea would be the creation of lookup tables for frequency selections between members of a net. The rules established for the SETAF network are the remote sites communicate with the other remote sites in their own network. When a remote site is unable to communicate with another remote site in its network, it is to leave a message on the bulletin board for the desired packet terminal. Communication between countries is a function that is performed by the gateway terminal.

III. POINTS OF DEPARTURE

SETAF is very interested in the operational capability for the Packet System. There have been a number of significant issues that are not fully explored. The first issue would be the requirement for encryption on the transmitted data. Encryption seems unnecessary on a communication system that is utilized for administrative traffic. Encryption with typical NSA approved hardware is not compatible with AX.25 protocols. The second significant issue is data rates that are acceptable. AX.25 does not define the data rate. Data rates are limited by the modem's ability to accurately pass error-free traffic over an HF channel. If the customer requires that large blocks of data be passed within a net, then serious consideration should be given to substituting a high speed modem with built in forward error correction. The substitution of the more efficient modem significantly enhances the system performance. Typical packet modems operate at 300 baud. Frequently the data contains errors resulting in the retransmission of the complete packet. The resulting throughput is more likely to be 150 baud. In the case of a modem that contains forward error correction, the data rates can be expanded to as high as 2400 baud. There is conservatively a ten to one improvement in information transport.

There are a number of high speed modems compatible with MIL-STD-188-110A that are presently available which can be inserted into a desktop MS-DOS computer. At the same time there exist software packages which perform the function of the terminal node controller. COMSEC hardware may be inserted into the computer making it possible to connect the computer directly to a radio like the Improved High Speed Radio (IHFR (AN/GRC-193)). Future packet systems can be resident in MS-DOS computers. Packet networks could be made operational simply by purchasing a number of specially configured computers and connecting the computer to existing HF radio assets.

Optimization of packet protocol should include the option of varying packet data lengths. Clear channels where propagation is not limiting data clarity should present an opportunity to extend the block length of each packet. AX.25 contains small data blocks and each block contains overhead data which really does not enhance communication. It is very inefficient to transmit redundant data and the operation of the network would be made considerable more effective by essentially changing the proportion of header data to actual message traffic. If the expectation

12.2.2

of clear error-free data is great, then the block length should be increased.

IV. APPLICATIONS

Every Army garrison whose personnel strength exceeds 400 is required to utilize a hardware system titled, "Standard Installation/Division Personnel Reporting System (SIDPERS)." SIDPERS is an Army-wide database of personnel information. It provides automated access to commanders and personnel managers, and it is a primary tool for controlling and reporting such things as personnel movements, promotions, unit strengths and eligibility in Army programs. Army policy requires that SIDPERS transactions take place within seven days. SETAF, because of its geographical dispersal and communication outages, has difficulties satisfying this requirement.

HF Packet radio is an ideal system for implementation into SIDPERS. A hardware interface could be built to transfer data files from SIDPERS to the packet radio. The packet radio could then transfer the file to the headquarters installation and the data system would be updated in either near real-time or at the worst with hours. This would significantly improve an important Army reporting system, and at the same time Army personnel that are stationed at some of these remote locations would feel less isolated and more in control of their career objectives.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The HF Packet Radio System installation was com-

Figure 4

pleted in September of 1991. Gateway sites were installed in Vicenza, Italy, and Cakmakly, Turkey. Remote packet terminals were installed in Perivolaki and Argypopolis, Greece, and Erzurum, Turkey. Voice communication was established at each site. Packet data routing was not quite as successful. Software hangups with the Gateway sites limited data communication. A portion of the problems at

the Gateway sites was related to incorrect settings of the

squelch dial on the transceiver. If the squelch dial is not adjusted properly, the terminal node controller sensed high noise level and determines that the channel is busy and does not transmit. Both Gateway sites have their antennas erected in high noise areas. The Vicenza antenna is located within 30 meters of high voltage power lines. The Cakmakli antenna is tied between two utility poles and is only 5 meters above ground. During the time of the installation, it was not possible to install the tuned loop antennas. The antennas at all the sites were Barker & Williamson (AC3.5-30) folded dipoles.

The installation of the packet radio demonstration system was plagued with difficulties. The electrical power in Erzurum had momentary interruption every two or three minutes. The Packet systems computer would have to reboot. A new message would be constructed, and then in the middle of a communication between Perivolaki, as an example, the power would fail and the computer would reboot and the communication would have to be reinitiated, only to fail again for the same reason. It very quickly became obvious that an uninterruptable power source would be necessary at the Erzurum facility.

All the problems encountered during the installation of the packet system were not resolved in September 1991. Personnel at the various sites were not able to devote a significant amount of time to become proficient with this new communication system. They are subject to rotational job assignments and the delivered packet network did not operate as a turn key system. SETAF is functioning as a test bed for HF packet technology. A follow-up trip to the various SETAF sites is planned. Operational changes in the packet software will be made at this time. The system documentation will be improved so that future operational difficulties will be resolvable in the field. During this time software changes will be made at each site so that the SETAF network is compatible with the Shape Technical Center's STC Packet Radio Initiative. At this point the SETAF sites, in addition to their own network, will be able to enter the STC network and thus will be able to communicate directly with CECOM.